

Research

The effect of Lazada e-service quality and e-recovery service quality on customer satisfaction

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Abstract: Nowadays, purchasing online has becoming a full part of our daily life and this is due to the development of the many technologies. Indonesia is actually the sixth country behind China on the first place, United States of America on the second place, Japan on the third place, followed by United Kingdom, and Germany; which use the most e-commerce. The title of this study is “The effect of Lazada e-service quality and e-recovery service quality on customer satisfaction” so its purpose is to analyse one by one the e-service quality, e-recovery service quality, and customer satisfaction, but especially to analyse the individual effect e-service quality and e-recovery service quality on customers’ satisfaction; and also the simultaneous effect of e-service quality and e-recovery service quality on customer satisfaction. The data for this study is gotten form a questionnaire which will be asked with 124 respondents and SPSS and multiple linear regression are used in order to achieve the analysis. The result shows that all items for each variables are valid and reliable; the normality test and heteroscedasticity test are good; F test shows that there is a simultaneous effect of e-service quality and e-recovery service quality on customer satisfaction; t test shows that there is an individual effect of e-service quality and e-recovery service quality on customer satisfaction; analysis of the coefficient of the determination shows that e-service quality and e-recovery service quality has 58,5% effect on customer satisfaction; the analysis of multiple linear regression.

Keywords: e-service quality, e-recovery service quality, customer satisfaction.

I- Introduction

In Indonesia, the use of the internet has begun to emerge and has increased sharply. The internet is making new discoveries and breakthroughs that aim to facilitate all activities in human life to begin to be created [1]. Indonesia is a big market for online stores itself, especially in Southeast Asia, with a large population and increasing internet users, one of the factors also along with the growth of smart phone users and the like which is an important part of Indonesian people to be able to transact on online shops [2]. The widespread growth of the Internet is information

technology that is used in conjunction with progress, this internet not only has a revolutionary impact on people's lives, but also its impact on business operations is proven [3]. Actually, most of the new generation use an internet in order to make their purchase so online shop system becomes more and more present in the daily life of the population especially in Indonesia [4]. Lazada is as well ranked as the ninth most visited site in Indonesia and become one of the references of the online buyer [5]. Actually Lazada faces some problems related with its customer because their customers keep complaining about the e-service offered by Lazada.

The objective of this study is to analyze the e-service quality offered by Lazada; the e-recovery service quality offered by Lazada; if the customer of Lazada are satisfied; the effect of the e-service quality offered by Lazada on its customer satisfaction; the effect of e-recovery service quality offered by Lazada on its customer satisfaction; and the simultaneous effect of the e-service quality and e-recovery service quality offered by Lazada on its customer satisfaction.

II- Literature review

2.1. E-service quality

Among one of the popular definition of e-service quality is that “e-service quality is the consumers’ overall evaluation and judgment of the excellence of the service offered by the company in the virtual marketplace [6]. Most of the study done about the e-service quality is focused on identifying the elements that give us customers’ perception of service quality, and especially building the models which will show the differences between customers’ expectations and the real service experience [7]. Improved e-service quality is very important because it is considered as an increasing profitability and ensure a continuity of the business in spite of the change in its environment [8]. E-service quality is also considered as the customers feeling that a company should offer on its service performance [9] [10]. And so e-service quality is the difference between expectations of service and perceived service, if the expectations are greater than the performance, then perceived quality is less than satisfactory and so customer dissatisfaction occurs. E-SERVQUAL is a method for measuring website e-service quality based on the online shoppers’ perceptions of how well the website meet their online transaction requirements. The scale contains the core scale which is e-service quality with four dimensions such as efficiency, fulfilment, reliability and privacy and the recovery scale which is e-recovery service quality with three dimensions such as responsiveness, contact and compensation [11]. E-service quality is the quality of service on line to which a website facilitates shopping, purchasing and efficient expenditure and

effective delivery. E-service quality is also a form of quality services developed affordability more extensive with the Internet media in order to connect the seller and buyers to meet the shopping activities effectively and efficiently [12]. E-service quality is a whole process from the beginning until the end of the transaction which include the looking for information; navigating the website; making orders; interaction with customer service; making delivery; and the feeling of satisfaction with the product ordered.

2.2. E-recovery service quality

The satisfaction of the customer is not always easy to achieve. It means that sometimes there is still failures. On this situation, the e-recovery service quality enters because e-service recovery quality only occurs when there is non-satisfaction from the customer. E-recovery service quality can be defining as a passive strategy for the improvement of customer satisfaction. So it refers to action taken by the firm in response to a service failure" [13]. Service recovery can be interpreted as a passive strategy in order to increase customer satisfaction. This activity is an effort and action taken by the company in order to respond to a service failure. So that each company must prepare a process for solving the problem in case that the customer complains [14]. An explanation which states that: "Service failures often occur when customers perceived service quality falls below customer expectations. For example, delivery and web site design problems are two major types of service failures in online retailing [15].

2.3. Customer satisfaction

Customer Satisfaction is a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment the resulting from comparing a product's perceived performance in relation to his or her expectations "[16] [17]. Looking on this definition, it can be concluded that customer satisfaction is a response from customers both feeling happy and disappointed that indicated customers for goods or services acquired and used. To successfulness and effectiveness of the implementation of the business activity of the company is can be reflected by the level of the satisfaction of the customer. Customer satisfaction is also referring to the "customer satisfaction with the purchase experience before with a website [18]. Customer satisfaction can be as well described as the gratification of the customer that comes from his or her earlier real buying experience with a certain electronic commerce company [19]. The satisfaction of the customer is essential for the creating of a long-term relationships with clients and sustaining profitability of online retailers. Satisfaction is a critical component in determining the success of online shopping, especially in B2C market [20],

and found that customer satisfaction can be also influenced by the quality of the user interface, because it provides physical proof of the online service provider`s capability as well as facilitating easy use of the online service. Website user interface design is especially very important because it has a strong association with the customer satisfaction [21]. Customer satisfaction is defined by the customer's response to the evaluation of perceived nonconformity between expectations and performance [22]. Customer satisfaction is a post-purchase evaluation where the perception of product performance exceeds customer expectations [23]. Customer satisfaction is an emotional state, their post-purchase reaction can be anger, dissatisfaction, irritation, excitement, and neutrality. Customer satisfaction has a direct relationship with customer loyalty, profits and market share. Customers if they are satisfied with the value provided by products and services, are likely to become customers for a long time [24].

III- Research framework

E-service quality and e-recovery service quality are both important and have an impact the customer satisfaction. Actually, e-service quality can greatly impact customer satisfaction [25]; *and also* it is important to solve the problems when the customers complain because service failures decrease customer satisfaction, and reduce their trust and commitment to firms [26], [27]. But after, e-recovery service quality, the customers are more satisfied than before. From those theory, the first hypothesis for this study is “*H1: E-service quality and e-recovery service quality have a simultaneous effect on customer satisfaction.*”

E-service quality plays an important rule when we talk about customer satisfaction. High-quality Internet services have numerous advantages and may lead to efficiency and benefits [29], [30]. Nowadays, e-service quality can greatly impact customer satisfaction [25]; and e-service quality is considered as an essential key of competitive advantage because it helps the company to retain and attract customers. So from that theory, we get the following second hypothesis which is “*H2: E-service quality has an effect on customer satisfaction.*”

Service failures occur when service performance cannot meet customer expectations during the delivery process; and e-recovery service quality is the solution of this service failure. It is important to solve the problems because service failures decrease customer satisfaction, and reduce their trust and commitment to firms [26], [27]. If customers are satisfied with the final recovery performance, they will be even happier than before. High service recovery efforts can significantly increase

customer post-failure levels of satisfaction [28]. From this theory, the third hypothesis for this study is “*H3: E-recovery service quality has an effect on customer satisfaction.*”

The research model for this study is as following:

IV- Methodology

In order to get the information which is essential, a questionnaire was done. It has four parts with 124 respondents, the first part is about the respondent demographic which are people living in Indonesia, the second part is about the e-service quality, the third part is about the e-recovery service quality and the last part is about the customer satisfaction. The independent variables for this study are e-service quality and e-recovery service quality; and the dependent variable is the customer satisfaction. In order to accomplish this study, SPSS is used to do all calculation. Some analysis is done such as the analysis of the average; reliability and validity test; normality test; heteroscedasticity test; F test; t test; coefficient of the determination; multiple linear regression.

V- Result and analysis

a. *Validity test for e-service quality, e-recovery service quality, and customer satisfaction*

Those following tables will show the validity test for each variables which are e-service quality, e-recovery service quality, and customer satisfaction.

Table 7: Validity test for e-service quality

Items	r correlation	r critical	Conclusion
X1	0,602	0,30	Valid
X2	0,439	0,30	Valid
X3	0,575	0,30	Valid
X4	0,602	0,30	Valid
X5	0,626	0,30	Valid
X6	0,472	0,30	Valid
X7	0,495	0,30	Valid
X8	0,498	0,30	Valid
X9	0,450	0,30	Valid

Source: primary data processed

Table 8: Validity test for e-recovery service quality

Items	r Correlations	r Critical	Conclusion
X10	0,438	0,30	Valid
X11	0,599	0,30	Valid
X12	0,426	0,30	Valid
X13	0,538	0,30	Valid
X14	0,637	0,30	Valid
X15	0,610	0,30	Valid
X16	0,641	0,30	Valid

Source: primary data processed

Table 9: Validity test for the customer satisfaction

Items	r Correlations	r Critical	Conclusion
X17	0,574	0,30	Valid
X18	0,643	0,30	Valid
X19	0,719	0,30	Valid

Source: primary data processed

From those tables, we can say that all items for the variables e-service quality, e-recovery service quality, and customer satisfaction, are valid because all of them are greater than 0,30.

b. Reliability test for e-service quality, e-recovery service quality, and customer satisfaction

This following table will show the reliability test for each variables which are e-service quality, e-recovery service quality, and customer satisfaction.

Table 10: Reliability test for e-service quality, e-recovery service quality, and customer satisfaction

	Cronbach`s Alpha	Cronbach`s Alpha based on Standardized items	N of items
E-service quality	0,885	0,886	9
E-recovery service quality	0,867	0,868	7
Customer satisfaction	0,890	0,893	3

Source: primary data processed

From the above table, we can see that the Cronbach`s Alpha obtained is 0,885 for e-service quality, 0,867 for e-recovery service quality, and 0,890 for customer satisfaction. Both of them are greater than 0,60 so that it is concluded that all items for each variable are reliable.

c. Analyse descriptive

From the calculation, we get those following tables which represents the average for each item on each variables. This following table shows the average for the variable e-service quality:

Table 13: Average for e-service quality

Variable	Indicators	Average for each indicators	Average variable
E-service quality	X1	3,853658537	3,615176152
	X2	3,62601626	
	X3	3,731707317	
	X4	3,62601626	
	X5	3,642276423	
	X6	3,43902439	
	X7	3,585365854	
	X8	3,536585366	
	X9	3,495934959	

Source: primary data processed

This table above shows that the average gotten from the respondent for the variable e-service quality is 3,61. It means that the e-service quality of Lazada is considered as a good position.

This following table shows the average for the variable e-recovery service quality:

Table 14: Average of e-recovery service quality

Variable	Indicators	Average for each indicators	Average variable
E-recovery service quality	X10	3,406504065	3,340301974
	X11	3,276422764	
	X12	3,544715447	
	X13	3,536585366	
	X14	3,504065041	
	X15	3,048780488	
	X16	3,06504065	

Source: primary data processed

This table above shows that the average gotten from the respondent for the variable e-recovery service quality is 3,34 which is a good position but relatively close to the neutral position.

This following table shows the average for the variable customer satisfaction:

Table 15: Average of customer satisfaction

Variable	Indicators	Average for each indicators	Average variable
Customer satisfaction	X17	3,43902439	3,490514905
	X18	3,520325203	
	X19	3,512195122	

Source: primary data processed

This table above shows that the average gotten from the respondent for the variable customer satisfaction is 3,49 which is a still a good position but still little far from the strongly good position. It means that the customer of Lazada are not yet enough satisfied about Lazada e-service quality and e-recovery service quality.

d. Normality test

A good regression model is one that has a normal or near normal distribution [31]. Normal distribution testing is done by looking at the histogram that compares observational data with a distribution that is near normal. The result for the normality test is as below:

Figure 15: Graph Normal P-P Plot

Source: Processed data

From the P-plot graph, we can see that the points follow the diagonal line so that it can be concluded that the regression meets the normality assumption.

e. Heteroscedasticity test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the regression model there is an unequal variance from the residuals of one observation to another [32]. A good regression model is one that homoscedasticity or heteroscedasticity does not occur.

Figure 16: Graph heteroscedasticity test

Source: Processed data

Based on the above test results, it can be seen that there is no heteroscedasticity in this regression model but there is homoscedasticity. So it is concluded that our regression is good.

f. F-test

F statistical test basically shows whether all independent variables entered in the model have a joint influence on the dependent variable. The calculated F value obtained from the regression results will be compared with the F table value, as well as comparing values with the significance level using $\alpha = 5\%$ (significant 5% or 0.05). The decision making criteria are: if F arithmetic \geq F table, then H0 is rejected; but if F arithmetic $<$ F table, then H0 is accepted.

Table 17: Result from ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	55.231	2	27.615	86.870	.000
	Residual	38.147	120	.318		
	Total	93.378	122			

Source: Processed data

Based on the above calculation results, it is known that the value of F arithmetic of 86,870 with a significance value of 0,000. With $\alpha = 0.05$ and $df1 = 2$ and $df2 = 120$, we get an F table of 3.07. Because the value of F arithmetic \geq F table. ($86,870 \geq 3.07$), then H0 is rejected. So e-service quality and e-recovery service quality have a simultaneous significant effect on customer satisfaction.

g. T test

This test is used to show how far the influence of one explanatory variable / Independent individually in explaining the variation of the dependent variable [32]. Significant rate using $\alpha = 5\%$. The decision making criteria are: if t arithmetic \geq t table, then H0 is rejected; but if t arithmetic $<$ t table, then H0 is accepted.

Table 18: Result from t test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(constant)	-.052	.280		-.184	.854		
	E-service quality	.417	.088	.340	4.764	.000	.670	1.493

e-recovery service quality	.610	.083	.522	7.322	.000	.670	1.493
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Source: Processed data

Based on the results of the SPSS analysis above, the results obtained from the testing of each hypothesis are:

- Hypothesis test for the effect of e-service quality (X1) on customer satisfaction (Y):

The result of t arithmetic based on the SPSS table for e-service quality (X1) variable is equal to 4.764 while the t table for df= 120 is 1.658. This shows that $t_{\text{arithmetic}} \geq t_{\text{table}}$ ($4,764 \geq 1,658$), therefore H_0 is rejected and it means that there is an effect of the e-service quality variable (X1) on customer satisfaction (Y).

- Hypothesis test for the effect of e-recovery service quality (X2) on customer satisfaction (Y):

The result of t arithmetic based on the SPSS table for e-recovery service quality (X2) variable is equal to 7,322 while the t table for df= 120 is 1.658. This shows that $t_{\text{arithmetic}} \geq t_{\text{table}}$ ($7,322 \geq 1,658$), therefore H_0 is rejected and it means that there is an effect of the e-recovery service quality variable (X2) on customer satisfaction (Y).

h. Analysis of the coefficient of determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination (R²) essentially measures how far the model's ability to explain variations in the dependent variable. The value of the coefficient of determination is zero and one.

Table 19: Result from the coefficient of determination

Mode	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.769	.591	.585	.5638225

Source: Processed data

From this result, we can see that e-service quality and e-recovery service quality have as much effect of 58,5% towards the customer satisfaction. As we see, it is already almost 60%, which means that e-service quality and e-recovery service occupy an important rule on the customer satisfaction of Lazada because only 41,5% is effected by the other possible variables.

i. Multiple linear regression analysis

The statistical analysis used in this study is multiple linear regression analysis using the SPSS 21 program. Multiple linear regression analysis to calculate the magnitude of the quantitative influence of a change (variable X) on other events (variable Y), then use the following formula:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$$

Where:

Y= Customer satisfaction

X 1= E-service quality

X 2= E-recovery service quality

B1, B2= regression coefficient

a= constant

e=error

Table 20: Result from SPSS for multiple linear regression

Model		Standardized coefficients
		B
1	(Constant)	
	E-service quality	.340
	E-recovery service quality	.522

Source: Processed data

Based on the result from SPSS, we get the following form of multiple linear regression equation:

$$Y = 0,340 X_1 + 0,522 X_2 + e$$

- From the equation above can be seen that there is an effect of e-service quality (X1) and e-recovery service quality (X2) on customer satisfaction (Y).
- The regression coefficient for the e-service quality(X1) variable is positive, indicating that if the value of e-service quality (X1) increases, the value of customer satisfaction (Y) will increase also; and if the value of e-service quality (X1) decreases, the value of customer satisfaction (Y) will decrease also.
- The regression coefficient for the e-recovery service quality(X2) variable is positive, indicating that if the value of e-recovery service quality (X2) increases, the value of

customer satisfaction (Y) will increase too; and if the value of e-recovery service quality (X2) decreases, the value of customer satisfaction (Y) will decrease too.

VI. Discussion and conclusion

This study is done in order to analyse the e-service quality, e-recovery service quality, customer satisfaction, effect of e-service quality on customer satisfaction, effect of e-recovery service quality on customer satisfaction, and effect of e-service quality and e-recovery service quality on customer satisfaction. For that we did a questionnaire which has four parts: the first part is about the profile of the respondent; the second part is about the e-service quality which has efficiency, fulfilment, system availability, and privacy as an indicator; the third part is about the e-recovery service quality which has responsiveness, contact, and compensation as an indicator; and the last part is about the customer satisfaction which has expectations, perceptions, and confirmation as an indicator.

- This study was done with the customers of Lazada which most of them are aged between 19 and 35 years old. It shows us that the customer of Lazada are young and active because we also saw that 43,8% of their customer are using their website at least once a day and 24,6% of the customer are using this website at least once a month. We have seen as well the frequency of purchase of the customer of Lazada where we get 36,4% of the customer have used lazada during the last year, 24% of the customer have used Lazada during the last six months, 22,5% of the customer of Lazada have used it during the last three months and 14,7% of the customer of Lazada have used it during the last month.
- The e-service quality offered by Lazada does not yet reach the strongly good position because they have gotten 3,61 which is a good position. It means that Lazada still need to improve their e-service quality.
- The e-recovery service quality offered by Lazada has gotten 3,34 which is still a good position but relatively close to the neutral position. It means that the e-recovery service quality offered by Lazada still need some improvement.
- The customer satisfaction of Lazada get an average of 3,49 by the customer which is not yet the best position. So we can say that the customer of Lazada are not yet so satisfied with the service offered by Lazada and for them the service is just acceptable but not satisfying.

- According to the result from the F test, e-service quality and e-recovery service quality have a simultaneous effect on customer satisfaction.
- According to the result from the T test, e-service quality has an effect on customer satisfaction; and e-recovery service quality has an effect on customer satisfaction too.
- 58,5% of customer satisfaction is influenced by the variables e-service quality and e-recovery service quality. So we can say that e-service quality and e-recovery service play a very important rule on the customer satisfaction.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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